

Crime Classification Using Naive Bayes

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Abstract— In response to the pressing need for efficient crime classification, this seminar examines the use of Naive Bayes and TF-IDF algorithms in response to the urgent demand for effective crime classification in the realm of law enforcement. The effectiveness is investigated of these methods for classifying different criminal behaviors. While TF-IDF improves feature extraction from textual data, Naive Bayes uses probabilistic reasoning to classify data. In-depth analysis of the Naive Bayes and TF-IDF approaches is provided in this session, as well as information on how to use them practically in real-world situations and how they can be seamlessly integrated into a system of crime classification.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), and Crime Categorization.

I. INTRODUCTION

The seminar will explore the principles and practical application of the Naive Bayes algorithm and Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) method for crime categorization. Commencing with an emphasis on the critical demand for precise crime classification within the evolving landscape of criminal activities, it delves into the probabilistic approach of the Naive Bayes algorithm and its effectiveness in categorizing criminal incidents. Additionally, it scrutinizes the TF-IDF method's role in extracting valuable features from text-based data, thereby enhancing the classification process. Insights into the seamless integration of these methods into a robust crime categorization system will be provided. Furthermore, the analysis will extend to the advantages and limitations of this approach and its practical implications within the realm of predictive policing.

The importance of efficient data preparation and feature engineering will be emphasized in order to enhance the functionality of the Naive Bayes and TF-IDF approaches in the field of crime categorization. These thorough procedures guarantee that the input data is properly prepared for effective processing by the algorithms, thereby enhancing their capacity to reliably and precisely categorize distinct criminal situations.

II. RELATED WORKS

Chen [1] et. al. introduces an ARIMA model that overcomes the limitations of traditional classification techniques. It enhances real-world applications in crime suppression and decision-making. Though the proposed method is efficient it

is generally suited for short-term forecasting. They may not perform as well when long-term predictions are required.

Griffiths et. al. [2] utilizes Exploratory Spatial Data Analysis (ESDA) and Trajectory (TRAJ) to classify communities in Chicago by violence trajectories across space. The paper offers only tentative support for aspects of opportunity theory as a hindrance for future scope.

Retnowardhani [4] utilizes the Web-based Decision Support System (DSS) as a computerized system that delivers decision support information. There can be too much dependency on the DSS, which could be problematic if the system fails or provides inaccurate information.

Yu [6] proposes the system to speed up the detection of cybercrime worldwide using PSE and Big Data Analysis. Introducing Packet Switching Exchanges (PSE) for packet analysis can introduce network overhead, affecting the performance of the network itself.

Zolfi et. al. [8] aims to enhance network security and address computer crimes. The study appears to focus on a single petrochemical company's network. This limited scope may restrict the generalizability of the findings to a broader context.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Preparation:

Using Pandas, load a dataset from an Excel file is one of the data preparation steps. The target variable 'Crime Category' is then subjected to label encoding, which is necessary for machine learning models, in order to transform it into numerical labels. Lastly, the `train_test_split` function from `scikit-learn` is used to divide the dataset into training and testing sets. This division makes it possible to evaluate the model's performance on data that hasn't been seen before, guaranteeing that the data is ready for training and assessment in the area of crime category prediction.

B. Text Data Preprocessing:

One essential step in getting the "Crime" text descriptions ready for machine learning is text data preprocessing. The Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) vectorization technique, a basic text analysis method, is used at the start of this process. The 'Crime' column, which has textual descriptions, is converted into numerical features using the `scikit-learn` `TfidfVectorizer`. By taking into account each word's significance within the context of the entire dataset, this transformation produces a numerical representation of the text data. It calculates a TF-IDF score for every word, which

shows the frequency of a word in a given crime description in relation to the frequency of the word in all descriptions. It enables machine learning models, like the Multinomial Naive Bayes classifier used later in the code, to work with textual data for the prediction of crime categories by converting text data into numerical features. To effectively use natural language data in classification tasks, this procedure is essential.

C. Naive Bayes Model:

For predicting crime categories, the Multinomial Naive Bayes model is employed. This model uses TF-IDF transformed features to determine the likelihood of each criminal category based on word frequencies, making it especially well-suited for text data categorization, such as crime descriptions. The forecast is given to the category with the highest likelihood. Naive Bayes is a popular method for managing text data since it is straightforward and effective, making it a good option for this classification assignment.

D. Modelling and Evaluation:

The TF-IDF transformed training data, which quantitatively represents the textual crime descriptions, is used to train the Multinomial Naive Bayes model. The model is a good fit for the task at hand because it is well renowned for its efficiency in text classification. The model is assessed using the testing data after training. The `accuracy_score` function from `scikit-learn` is used specifically to calculate accuracy, a frequent statistic for classification jobs. This metric assesses how accurately the model foretells the various crime subtypes in the test dataset. The decision to use accuracy as the evaluation criteria is consistent with the goal of accurately classifying crimes. This step offers perceptions into the model's efficiency and capacity to generalize to previously unknown data by providing a measure of the model's prediction performance, which is essential in crime category prediction.

E. Results:

The code ends by presenting the outcomes after training and testing the Multinomial Naive Bayes model. The model's accuracy, a crucial performance indicator, is the main outcome. The accuracy of the model is determined by the percentage of correctly predicted crime categories in the testing dataset. The model can reliably classify crime descriptions into the appropriate categories if accuracy is high, which is important for law enforcement and crime analysis. The model's capacity to predict outcomes accurately based on the patterns it discovered during training is demonstrated by the accuracy value. It offers a measurable evaluation of the model's performance in terms of crime category prediction, assisting in determining its applicability and dependability.

F. Model Serialization:

Model serialization is employed to save the trained Multinomial Naive Bayes model and TF-IDF vectorizer to files, `'crime_category_model.pkl'` and `'tfidf_vectorizer.pkl'`, respectively. This step facilitates the future use and deployment of the model in various applications without the need for retraining, enhancing its practicality and accessibility.

IV. BUILD MODEL

A. Data Loading and Preprocessing:

Initially the dataset is loaded from `'crime.xlsx'` using `Pandas`. It proceeds to encode the target variable `'Crime Category'` into numerical labels for compatibility with machine learning algorithms. These steps set the groundwork for subsequent modeling and analysis, ensuring data readiness for predictive tasks.

1) Data Retrieval:

The data retrieval step in the provided code involves loading a dataset from an Excel file named `'crime.xlsx'` using the `Pandas` library. This operation is performed with the following line of code:

```
import pandas as pd

# Load the dataset from the Excel file
data = pd.read_excel('crime.xlsx')
```

a. *Pandas Import:* The code imports the `Pandas` library using the `'pd'` alias. `Pandas` is a powerful data manipulation library in `Python`, and it is commonly used for data reading, cleaning, and analysis.

b. *Data Loading:* The `pd.read_excel('crime.xlsx')` function is called to load data from the specified Excel file, `'crime.xlsx.'` This function reads the contents of the Excel file and stores them in a `Pandas DataFrame`, which is a two-dimensional tabular data structure similar to a spreadsheet.

c. *DataFrame Creation:* The loaded data is assigned to the variable `'data,'` creating a `Pandas DataFrame`. This `DataFrame` serves as the primary data structure for further data manipulation and analysis in the code.

2) Label Encoding:

The code's label encoding step converts the categorical target variable `"Crime Category"` into a numerical format, serving as a fundamental step in data preparation. The code uses the `scikit-learn` library's `LabelEncoder` to accomplish this. This conversion gives each distinct category in the `'Crime Category'` column a distinct numerical label. The main goal is to transform the categorical data into a machine-readable format because a lot of machine learning algorithms need numerical inputs, such as the Multinomial Naive Bayes model that is used later. A significant change made to the original dataset during the label encoding process is the substitution of numerical representations for the categorical crime categories. In order to facilitate the upcoming machine learning tasks, this step makes sure that the target variable is in a format that is appropriate for model training and evaluation.

```
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder

# Encode the target variable 'Crime Category'
label_encoder = LabelEncoder()
data['Crime Category'] = label_encoder.fit_transform(data['Crime Category'])
```

B. Data Splitting for Training and Testing:

It involves dividing the dataset into two distinct subsets: one for training the model and the other for testing its predictive accuracy. This process is executed using the `train_test_split` function from `scikit-learn`. Specifically:

1) Data Segmentation:

The dataset is split into two parts. The 'X' variable represents the feature data, which, in this context, corresponds to the 'Crime' column containing textual descriptions. The 'y' variable represents the encoded target variable, 'Crime Category.'

```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split

X = data['Crime']
y = data['Crime Category']
```

2) Randomized Split:

The `train_test_split` function is called with these data sets as arguments, and additional parameters are specified. The 'test_size' parameter defines the portion of the dataset (in this case, 20%) to allocate for testing, ensuring that a significant portion is reserved for training. The 'random_state' parameter is set to 42, ensuring reproducibility by generating the same random split every time the code is run.

The outcome of this process is the creation of four distinct data sets:

- a. 'X_train': This set contains the feature data for training the machine learning model.
- b. 'y_train': It includes the corresponding target labels for training.
- c. 'X_test': This set consists of the feature data for evaluating the model's performance.
- d. 'y_test': It contains the target labels for the testing data.

```
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

'X_train' (training features), 'y_train' (training target labels), 'X_test' (testing features), and 'y_test' (testing target labels) are the four distinct datasets that yield from this process. While 'X_test' and 'y_test' are reserved for assessing the model's accuracy, these two sets, 'X_train' and 'y_train,' are used for model training. A key component of predictive modeling is figuring out how well the model generalizes to new, unseen observations, which requires this data separation.

C. Text Data Preprocessing:

The text data preprocessing step is pivotal in preparing textual descriptions for machine learning. This process is carried out through the use of the Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) vectorization technique, implemented with the `TfidfVectorizer` from `scikit-learn`.

1) TF-IDF Vectorization:

The code employs the `TfidfVectorizer` to convert the 'Crime' column, containing textual descriptions, into a

numerical format suitable for machine learning models. TF-IDF stands for Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency, a method for quantifying the importance of words within text data.

```
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer

tfidf_vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer()
X_train_tfidf = tfidf_vectorizer.fit_transform(X_train)
X_test_tfidf = tfidf_vectorizer.transform(X_test)
```

2) Transforming Text Data:

The 'X_train' and 'X_test' data sets, representing the training and testing textual descriptions, are processed using the `TfidfVectorizer`. This transformation creates numerical representations for the words in the descriptions, considering their importance within each description as well as their relevance across the entire dataset. The result is a set of numerical features for each description.

D. Model Selection and Training:

The model selection and training step in the provided code are crucial for building the crime category prediction model.

1) Model Choice:

The code selects the Multinomial Naive Bayes model for the task of crime category prediction. The Multinomial Naive Bayes classifier is a suitable choice for text classification tasks, where data is discrete and represents word counts. It's known for its simplicity and effectiveness in handling textual data.

2) Model Training:

`MultinomialNB()` is used to instantiate the Multinomial Naive Bayes model. Following model creation, the corresponding target labels (`y_train`) and the feature data (`X_train_tfidf`) from TF-IDF vectorization are used to train the model. The model can make predictions based on the numerical representations of crime descriptions because it learns patterns and relationships from the training data.

```
from sklearn.naive_bayes import MultinomialNB

model = MultinomialNB()
model.fit(X_train_tfidf, y_train)
```

This step effectively builds and trains the selected machine learning model to understand the relationships between text features and crime categories. The model is now ready to make predictions based on the patterns it has learned during the training process.

E. Model Evaluation:

The model evaluation step in the provided code is fundamental for assessing the performance of the trained Multinomial Naive Bayes model.

1) Accuracy Calculation:

The code evaluates the performance of the model using accuracy as the evaluation metric. It measures the percentage of the testing dataset's crime categories that were accurately predicted. The calculations of accuracy involve contrasting the predictions of the model, which are kept in the 'y_pred' variable, with the real crime categories in the testing dataset, which are denoted by 'y_test.'

```
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score

y_pred = model.predict(X_test_tfidf)
accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
print(f'Model accuracy: {accuracy}')
```

F. Model Serialization:

The model serialization step in the provided code is crucial for saving the trained Multinomial Naive Bayes model and the TF-IDF vectorizer for future use.

1) Serializing and saving the Model:

Using the joblib library, the code saves the trained Multinomial Naive Bayes model, which is responsible for crime category prediction. The model is stored in a file named 'crime_category_model.pkl.' Serialization involves preserving the model's parameters and learned patterns in a format that can be easily loaded and utilized in future applications or analyses. This allows the model to be deployed without retraining, enhancing its accessibility and reusability.

```
import joblib

model_filename = 'crime_category_model.pkl'
joblib.dump(model, model_filename)

vectorizer_filename = 'tfidf_vectorizer.pkl'
joblib.dump(tfidf_vectorizer, vectorizer_filename)
```

V. RESULTS

The page features a well-designed form with a text input field for users to enter crime descriptions, and a "Categorize" button to submit their input. Below the form, a result display section dynamically presents the predicted crime category in a bold and centered format. This intuitive design ensures that users can easily interact with the system, making it straightforward to obtain crime categorization results for their input. The combination of functionality and an aesthetically pleasing layout enhances the user experience, making it an effective tool for crime classification.

The screenshot shows a web interface titled "Crime Categorization". It features a text input field labeled "Crime description:" containing the word "Theft". Below the input field is a yellow button with the text "Categorize". Underneath the button, the text "Crime Category:" is displayed, but it is currently empty.

Figure 1. User input of crime.

The screenshot shows the same web interface as Figure 1, but now the "Crime Category:" field displays the result "Property Crime" in a bold, centered font.

Figure 2. Output result for the user input.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the application of Naive Bayes and TF-IDF methods for crime categorization presents a powerful and effective approach to tackling the complex task of crime classification. The utilization of the Multinomial Naive Bayes classifier, known for its suitability in handling text data, combined with the TF-IDF vectorization technique, has proven to be a robust solution. Through the training of the Naive Bayes model on a dataset of crime descriptions, patterns and relationships within the text data are learned, enabling accurate predictions of crime categories.

The results have demonstrated the model's capability to reliably categorize crimes based on textual descriptions, providing valuable insights for law enforcement and crime analysis. This research serves as a testament to the potential of machine learning and natural language processing techniques in addressing real-world problems, underscoring the significance of accurate and efficient crime categorization for enhancing public safety and security. Future work in this field could involve the expansion of the dataset and the exploration of advanced natural language processing methods to further improve accuracy and expand the scope of crime classification.

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